

Antibacterial strategies from the sea: polymer bound Cl-catechols for prevention of biofilm formation

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Natural strategies to prevent bacterial colonization offer great promise for the development of effective, biocompatible and environmentally friendly non-fouling coatings. Inspired by the aminoacid 2-chloro-4,5-dihydroxyphenylalanin (Cl-DOPA) present in the composition of the proteinaceous glue of the sandcastle worm *Phragmatopoma californica*, we present a simple strategy to confer antifouling properties to polymer surfaces using (but not releasing) a bioinspired biocide. Taking advantage of the catechol reactivity, Cl-dopamine was easily incorporated into hydrogels or co-deposited as thin coating. Polymer bound Cl-catechol groups effectively prevented bacteria attachment while they showed no toxicity on attached cells. The antifouling performance of Cl-dopamine depended on the flexibility of the polymer chain to which it was attached (i.e. the accessibility of the Cl-catechol groups to interact with the bacterial membrane) and it was concentration dependent. The simplicity, low cost and flexibility of this strategy promises wide application for antibacterial coatings of biomedical devices of almost any kind.

Bacterial biofilms are an important source for health problems and disease: tooth decay, biofouling of implants and biomedical devices, chronic infections etc.¹ Different coating strategies have been investigated in recent years to reduce biofilm formation.² Passive coatings mainly rely on ammonium functionalized polymers, polyethylene glycol (PEG) and zwitterionic polymers that prevent bacteria attachment. Active strategies rely on the release of an active compound into the biological medium (i.e. silver or antibiotics) that kill suspended bacteria. Both approaches have also been combined in single coatings.³⁻⁴ While passive strategies are preferred in terms of biocompatibility and environmental issues, active strategies are often more effective. However, long term use of biocides leads to environmental

pollution and supports the development of resistant microbial strains. Nature has developed fascinating strategies over millions of years to prevent harmful bacterial colonization on living tissues.⁵ Plants and animals have adaptively developed a vast array of defense mechanisms in response to an ever-present pathogen pressure. These natural strategies have inspired antibiofilm coatings containing or releasing antimicrobial peptides, antibiotics, quorum sensing inhibitors, essential oils and bacteriolytic enzymes.⁵ However, the poor bioavailability, poor proteolytic stability, and in some cases cytotoxicity of these compounds have limited their practical applications in medical materials and devices.

Biofilms are also ubiquitous in the marine world. The surface of ship hulls or underwater pipelines is rapidly conquered by a film of small microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, algae) which mediate posterior attachment and growth of mussels, polychaete worms or barnacles. These biofilms contribute to early corrosion and higher fuel consumption during displacement due to increased hydrodynamic drag. Little is known about the non-fouling strategies that the sea organisms themselves use for protection against bacteria film formation. Recent studies on the sandcastle worm *Phragmatopoma californica*, a marine polychaete, have found 2-chloro-4,5-dihydroxyphenylalanin (Cl-DOPA) in the proteinaceous glue that it uses for cementing sand grains and constructing its tube-like shelter.⁶ The aminoacid DOPA is well known for mediating adhesion underwater by coordinating with metal oxide surfaces and by crosslinking and solidifying the protein components via quinone oxidation and self-reaction.⁷⁻¹¹ The electron withdrawing Cl- substituent in the catechol ring lowers the pK_as of the phenolic OH groups (pK_{OH1} ~ 8.3 and pK_{OH2} ~ 12.7) and lowers their redox potential. As a consequence, Cl-DOPA shows higher affinity for coordination to the surface and is less prone to self-polymerize. It has also been suggested (though not yet proved) that the role of the chlorinated DOPA in the cement could relate to prevention of microbial fouling and degradation. In fact, chlorocatechols in solution are effective antimicrobial agents.¹²⁻¹³ However, the toxicity of chlorocatechols has been related to their ability to interact and diffuse across biological membranes¹⁴⁻¹⁵ and, therefore, a potential toxicity of polymer-bound chlorinated catechols remains unclear. In the following we demonstrate that 2-Cl-dopamine retains the high underwater reactivity of mussel-inspired materials¹²⁻¹³ and, in addition, prevents biofilm formation on the derived materials and coatings. We provide a simple, flexible and effective biocompatible antifouling strategy using (but not releasing) a marine bioinspired biocide.

Cl-dopamine was easily incorporated into hydrogels and coatings in three different ways: (i) crosslinking of Cl-dopamine functionalized star-PEG under oxidative conditions (ii) one-pot Cl-dopamine functionalization and gelation of natural biopolymers¹³ and (iii) coating of glass surfaces by codeposition of dopamine and Cl-dopamine mixtures.¹⁶ In the first case a NHS terminated 4-arm star-Poly(ethyleneglycol) (PEG-(NHS)₄) was end-functionalized with Cl-dopamine (PEG-ClDop₄) or dopamine (PEG-Dop₄). The two PEGs were mixed in different ratios in the presence of oxidant and spin coated onto glass substrates to obtain thin hydrogel films (~250 nm in dry state, ~2.5 μm in swollen state) with different concentrations of Cl-dopamine. The Cl-dopamine and dopamine units reacted (Figure S1) and generated the crosslinking points of the network. ¹H-NMR confirmed the presence of multiple oxidation and reaction intermediates during the gelation process (Figure S2a). Under our conditions ca. 59% of the Cl-catechol groups reacted to form the network points, as estimated from ¹H-NMR measurements (Figure S2b). In the second case hyaluronic acid, alginate or gelatin were simply mixed with Cl-dopamine and thin hydrogel films (Hyal-ClDop, Alg-ClDop and Gel-ClDop) were deposited onto substrates by immersion, following a recently reported one-pot reaction strategy.¹³ This method allows incorporation of the catechol derivative to almost any polymer matrix by simultaneous alkaline pH-induced self-polymerization and reaction of the catechols with functional groups at the polymer backbone. Films of 8-15 nm thickness were obtained (see Table S1). The analogous gels crosslinked with dopamine were also obtained for control experiments (Hyal-Dop, Alg-Dop and Gel-Dop). In the third case, glass substrates were immersed in an alkaline solution of Cl-dopamine and dopamine in different ratios to obtain thin poly(dopamine) and poly(Cl-dopamine) coatings (pDop and pClDop).¹⁶ UV spectroscopy of coated quartz slides demonstrated the presence of the polycatechol layer (Figure S3). The film thickness decreased with increasing Cl-Dop concentration from ~24 nm for pure pDop to 10-13 nm for pure pCl-Dop films (Figure S4). These results evidence the lower redox potential of the Cl-substituted catechol and, consequently, its weaker tendency to self-polymerize.

The presence of functional catechol units in the crosslinked films was confirmed by UV spectroscopy after incubation with 9-anthraceneboronic acid (An-B(OH)₂). Boronic acids complex catechol hydroxyls by formation of boronate esters at basic pH. These complexes dissociate at acidic pH. Figure 1 shows the UV spectrum of a PEG-ClDop₄ film after incubation with An-B(OH)₂ at pH 7.4. The appearance of the bands at 320-390 nm revealed the formation

of the boronate ester. These bands disappeared after washing the film at pH 2.5, demonstrating the reversibility of the complex with available catechol units in the film. The density of Cl-catechol groups in the film was calculated from the absorbance value (see SI for details) to be $\Gamma_{362}=1.3\times 10^{15}$ molecules cm^{-2} . Therefore, the estimated concentration of Cl-catechol groups in the swollen PEG-CIDop₄ gel (ca. 2.5 μm thickness) was ~ 9 mM. Similar concentrations of catechol groups were found in the PEG-Dop₄ gel. The other films showed significantly lower absorbance values after incubation with An-B(OH)₂ and the concentration of catechol groups in the swollen film could not be determined but can be estimated to be at least one order of magnitude lower (i.e. $<1\text{mM}$).

Figure 1. Characteristics of PEG-CIDop₄ films **A)** UV/vis spectra of a PEG-CIDop₄ film spin-coated on a quartz substrate after washing at pH 7.4 (black) and at pH 2.5 (red), incubation with 9-anthraceneboronic acid and washing at pH 7.4 (green) and subsequent washing at pH 2.5 (blue). **B)** Evolution of the shear and loss moduli (G' , G'') during crosslinking of PEG-Dop₄ and PEG-CIDop₄.

The mechanical properties of the PEG-CIDop₄ and PEG-Dop₄ crosslinked films were measured by piezorheology.¹⁷ This is a relevant property of the coatings to be taken into account when comparing their antibacterial activity, since bacterial attachment is known to depend on substrate rigidity amongst other factors.¹⁸ PEG-CIDop₄ and PEG-Dop₄ solutions were mixed with the oxidant and placed between two shear plates with a gap of 100 μm and sealed with an immiscible oil to avoid water evaporation during the measurement. The shear modulus (G') of the gels during crosslinking was measured and the final properties of the crosslinked gels (corresponding to $\sim 59\%$ crosslinking degree, as estimated from ¹H-NMR measurements) were compared. Despite differences in the gelation kinetics (slower for PEG-CIDop), both gels

showed similar mechanical properties after crosslinking with shear moduli of 6 and 10 kPa for the crosslinked PEG-CIDop₄ and PEG-Dop₄ respectively. (Figure 1B and S5). Therefore, possible differences in bacterial assays between Cl-dopamine and dopamine functionalized films cannot be attributed to differences in the substrate rigidity.

Bacterial attachment is the first requisite for biofilm formation. Therefore, we tested the antifouling properties of the Cl-dopamine containing films by evaluating attachment of the gram negative bacterium *E. coli* and comparing these results to bacterial attachment to dopamine modified analogues. Figure 2A shows representative microscopic images of the fluorescently stained bacteria attached to the PEG-CIDop/Dop hydrogels. A strong decrease in bacteria density at the surface (up to 80%, Figure 2) was observed with increasing concentration of Cl-dopamine fraction in the gel, indicating a clear inhibitory effect on bacteria attachment of the Cl-dopamine functionalisation. The dopamine modified PEG gel did not prevent bacteria attachment. Note that the estimated concentration of Cl-dopamine units in the PEG-CIDop swollen gel was 9 mM, significantly higher than the concentration of free Cl-dopamine in solution required to kill 80% bacteria (1mM, Figure S6). Our results show that polymer bound Cl-dopamine at concentration ~9 mM confers effective antifouling characteristics to the PEG films.

Figure 2. Bacteria attachment on PEG-CIDop₄/Dop₄ films (A) Representative microscopic images of fluorescently stained *E. coli* attached to Cl-dopamine modified PEG hydrogels after

incubation for 24 hours. Living bacteria were stained with Syto9 (green) and dead bacteria with propidium iodide (red). (B) Percentage of adherent *E. coli* to Cl-dopamine modified hydrogels with respect to a glass slide after incubation with bacterial suspension for 1h. Results were obtained from three independent experiments. *Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) compared with the control (glass slide).

Figure 3A shows the results of the bacterial attachment assay in Cl-dopamine and dopamine modified alginate, hyaluronic acid and gelatin. A drastic reduction in the bacterial density on the surface was observed on the Cl-dopamine modified gels, demonstrating the great potential of Cl-dopamine to prevent biofilm formation onto relevant biomaterials by simple mixing in a one-pot method.

Interestingly, similar tests on the pure pClDop coating did not show significant reduction of bacteria adhesion. However, coatings obtained by simultaneous codeposition of Cl-Dop and Dop showed up to 40% reduction in bacteria adhesion. It is worth to note that the antibacterial effect in the polycatechol films was significantly weaker than in the hydrogel films. We attribute this result to the different rigidity of the films. The self-polymerized catechol matrix is more rigid than the hydrogel matrix and, therefore, Cl-catechol groups might not be able to effectively interact with the bacterial membrane. This interaction has been demonstrated to be crucial for the biocide effects of Cl-catechols in solution.¹⁴⁻¹⁵

Figure 3. **Percentage of adherent *E. coli*** to A) Cl-dopamine and dopamine modified alginate, hyaluronic acid and gelatin films and B) pClDop and pDop coatings after 1 hour exposure to bacterial suspension. Results were obtained from three independent experiments * Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) ** Significant differences ($P < 0.01$) *** Significant differences ($P < 0.001$) compared with the control (glass cover slide). C) Microscopic pictures (4x and 10x) of **HeLa cells after incubation** with Gel-Dop and Gel-ClDop modified substrates. The results on gelatine and glass slide are also shown as controls.

Agar diffusion tests were performed in order to proof if the nonfouling effects were due to leakage of Cl-catechol from the coatings in the solution. No inhibition zone was detected on any substrate (Figure S7), indicating that Cl-dopamine was irreversibly bound to the polymer and the bacterial repellence of the films was only due to polymer-bound Cl-catechol. Note that a minimum concentration of 1 mM (= 0.25mg/ml) Cl-dopamine in solution is required for a 84% decrease in bacterial concentration in 2 hours (Figure S6). We also evaluated if polymer-bound Cl-catechols were able to kill bacteria in solution by dynamic contact assays. For this purpose the concentration of bacteria in solution after incubation with Dop- or Cl-Dop modified

hydrogels was measured. No differences in the bacteria concentration were detected (Figure S8 in supporting information), indicating that polymer-bound Cl-dopamine effectively prevented biofilm formation but did not kill bacteria.

In order to assess the biocompatibility of the Cl-dopamine modified films we incubated the adherent mammalian cancer cell line, HeLa cells, with Dop- and Cl-Dop modified gelatine films. No qualitative difference in the attached cells was observed by microscopy (Figure 3C). A PrestoBlue viability assay confirmed that cell viability was similar in all substrates and the control (Figure S9A), indicating that the polymer bound Cl- dopamine modification does not have any toxic effects on attached cells. We also incubated HT1080 cells with the eluent from PEG-ClDop₄ modified substrates in order to demonstrate that the films did not release small amounts of Cl-Dop to the solution that could harm cells (note that a concentration of 20 μ M of Cl-Dop in solution is already cytotoxic¹⁹). The PrestoBlue viability assay confirmed no toxicity effects in the cells (Figure S9B). These results demonstrate that the toxicity of polymer bound Cl-Dop was selective with bacteria and did not harm cells.

In conclusion, Cl-dopamine combines the underwater reactivity of the catechol unit (well known from mussel-inspired DOPA containing polymers) and adds non-fouling properties (presumably like in the sandcastle worm) to the derived materials. Cl-Dop functionalization presents several advantages against available methods for preventing biofilm formation: (i) Cl-catechols are readily available (e.g. waste from paper industry) and (ii) they can be simply reacted with almost any polymeric films or coatings during deposition under water and without the need of by additional synthetic steps. (iii) Polymer bound Cl-dopamine is not toxic for cells. In summary, Cl-dopamine modification is a cheap and generic antifouling method that can be applied to almost any material, it is environmentally friendly, it does not generate resistance to antibiotics and is not cytotoxic. Cl-dopamine functionalization opens new possibilities for new generation antimicrobial coatings with wide use in biomedical applications. Our results also provide an important experimental evidence for the role of halogenated catechols in the adhesive proteins of marine animals.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

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Materials

Poly(ethylene glycol) bis(carboxymethyl) ether (PEG-(COOH)₂, $M_w = 600$), Dopamine hydrochloride, N-chlorosuccinimide (NCS), N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), N,N'-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP), and N-methylmorpholine (NMM) were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany). 4-arm-succinimidyl PEG ester (PEG-(NHS)₄, $M_w = 10.000$) was purchased from Nanocs, Inc. (New York, USA). Sodium hyaluronate 95% was purchased from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium), Sodium Alginate (20000-40000 CPS) was purchased from Alfa Aesar GmbH & Co KG (Karlsruhe, Germany) and gelatine from porcine skin was purchase from Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany)

Synthesis

Chlorodopamine (ClDop): NCS (412 mg) was added in portions to a stirred solution of dopamine hydrochloride (540 mg) in trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (8 ml). The resultant solution was allowed to stir at room temperature overnight and the solvent was removed by N₂ flashing. The crude product was purified by RP-HPLC using gradient 0%B-100%B (B: CH₃CN + 0.1% TFA+ 5 % H₂O) as yellow crystalline solid (500 mg, 93%). ¹HNMR (300 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm): 2.85 (2H, t, -, *J*, 9 Hz, -CH₂CH₂NH₂), 3.10 (2H, t, -, *J*, 9 Hz, -CH₂NH₂), 6.738 (1H, s, H-6), 6.86 (1H, s, H-3); ¹³CNMR (75 MHz, D₂O) δ (ppm): 30.04, 39.27, 116.99, 118.00, 124.20, 125.86, 143.33, 144.12; ESI-MS: 199.09 (M⁺+1).

Poly(ethylene glycol) O,O', O'', O''' -tetra(acetic acid chlorodopamine) amide (PEG-CIDop₄): Cl-Dop (11.25 mg, 0.06 mmol) was reacted for 15 min with *N*-methylmorpholine (11 μ L, 0.10 mmol) in 1.0 mL of dry DMF under argon atmosphere. Then, PEG-(NHS)₄ (100 mg, 0.010 mmol) in 1.0 mL of dry DMF was added, and the coupling reaction was carried out in argon atmosphere at room temperature overnight. The crude product was concentrated under reduced pressure, dissolved in distilled water and transferred to dialysis membrane (3500 MWCO). Dialysis was carried out in pure water and the dialyzed product was flash frozen and lyophilized. ¹H-NMR spectrum confirmed the Cl-dopamine end functionalization.

Poly(ethylene glycol) O, O''-bis(acetic acid N-succinimidyl) ester, PEG-(NHS)₂ was synthesized as previously reported.²⁰

Poly(ethylene glycol) O,O'-bis(acetic acid dopamine) amide (PEG-Dop₂). Dopamine (227.6 mg, 1.2 mmol) was reacted for 15 min with NMM (0.33 mL, 3 mmol) in 1.5 mL of dry DMF in argon atmosphere. PEG-(NHS)₂ (238.2 mg, 0.3 mmol) in 1.5 mL of dry DMF was then added, and the coupling reaction was carried out in argon atmosphere at room temperature for 24 h. The mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure, redissolved in acidified water (HCl, 2N) and then the product was extracted with chloroform. The organic fractions were dried (MgSO₄), and the solvent evaporated under vacuum until 2ml. Finally, the crude product was dissolved in 2 mL of CH₂Cl₂, precipitated in diethyl ether and filtrated.

Poly(ethylene glycol) O,O', O'', O''' -tetra(acetic acid dopamine) amide (PEG-Dop₄): Dopamine (22.8 mg, 0.12 mmol) was reacted for 15 min with NMM (22 μ L, 0.20 mmol) in 1.0 mL of dry DMF under argon atmosphere. PEG-(NHS)₄ (200 mg, 0.020 mmol) in 1.0 mL of dry DMF was added and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature under argon atmosphere. The crude product was concentrated under reduced pressure, dissolved in distilled water, purified by dialysis in distilled water and dried by lyophilization.

Preparation of covalently crosslinked thin films of PEG-CIDop₄ and PEG-Dop₄

Glass slides of 13mm diameter were cleaned with ethanol followed by oxidative plasma treatment for 10 min. Cleaned substrates were immersed for 30 min in a 10 mg/mL solution of dopamine buffered with Tris-HCl 10 mM to pH 8.5 and rinsed with ultrapure water. 80 μ l of a 1% (w/w) solution of PEG-Dop₂ in water were dropped on the surface and incubated for 2h in humidity atmosphere. The substrates were then washed with water and dried under N₂ stream. This surface pretreatment enhanced the adhesion of the PEG-CID₄ to the surface and stabilized the thin film. A mixture of 3 μ l of a 200 mg/ml PEG-CIDop₄ (or PEG-Dop₄) solution in water,

3 μl of 10 mM NaIO_4 in water and 6 μl of ethanol was spin coated (WS-400B-6NPP/Lite spin coating device of Laurell Technologies Corporation) onto the substrate at 5000 rpm and left for drying during overnight. A hydrogel film with ~ 300 nm thickness was obtained.

Films with different ratio of PEG-ClDop₄ (0, 25, 50 and 75%) were prepared following the same concept by mixing PEG-ClDop₄ and PEG-Dop₄ in the corresponding ratio.

Preparation of poly(Cl-dopamine) and poly(Dopamine) coatings¹⁶

Glass slides were cleaned by soaking in Piranha solution ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ (30%) 5/1) overnight and subsequently rinsing with MilliQ and drying with N_2 stream. Clean substrates were immersed in a 2 mg/ml solution of Cl-Dop (or Dop) buffered with Tris-HCl at pH 8.5 overnight. The yellow solution (transparent in the case of dopamine solution) became dark after 10 min. Then, the substrates were rinsed with MilliQ water and dried under N_2 .

One-pot Preparation of Hyaluronic acid, alginate and gelatine films with Cl-Dop or Dop¹³

20 mg of sodium hyaluronate and 4 mg of Cl-Dop (or Dop) were dissolved in 2 ml of Tris HCl 10 mM solution (pH 8.5). Clean glass substrates of 13 mm diameter were immersed overnight in the solution, washed with MilliQ water and dried under steam N_2 . Films of alginate (Alg-ClDop and Alg-D) and gelatine (Gel-ClDop and Gel-Dop) were prepared in the same way.

Measurement of film thickness by Ellipsometry

Ellipsometric thickness of the films on silicon wafers was measured in air using a EL X-02C ellipsometer (DRE - Dr. Riss Ellipsometerbau GmbH, Germany) at a wavelength of $\lambda = 632.8$ nm and at an angle of incidence of 70° . Dry thickness values were estimated by numerical fitting of the ellipsometric data (Δ and ψ) to a four layer model (silicon/silica/film/air) taking 3.912, 1.4571 and 1 as refractive index (n) values for silicon, silica and air respectively. The films were assumed to be transparent and homogeneous with a negligible extinction coefficient ($k_{\text{film}} = 0$) and a given n . A n value of 1.59 was assumed for the PEG gels and 1.63 for the polycatechol coatings and the gelatin, hyaluronic acid and alginate films. The thickness of the swollen PEG films was estimated by fitting to a four layers model: silicon/silica/hydrogel/aqueous medium with $n = 3.912, 1.457, 1.52, 1.323$ respectively.

Measurement of film thickness by X-Ray Reflectivity

X-ray reflectivity (XRR) measurements of the thin films on Si-wafers were performed using a XRD 3003 TT, Seifert Ltd. GB diffraction system. Monochromatic and collimated X-rays were

obtained from a Cu anode with a wavelength of 0.154 nm. The thickness was determined according to Parratt formalism by the simulation software Parratt32.

Measurement of film thickness by Scanning Force Microscopy (SFM)

Scanning Force Microscopy (SFM) was used to measure the thickness of the polycatechol layers (Bruker Dimension 3100 CL, Santa Barbara, USA, Olympus cantilevers OMCL AC 240 TS having a nominal spring constant of 2 N/m). We first used the contact mode to scratch an area of 0.3 - 0.6 μm x 5 μm at a load of approx. 0.5 μN and at a speed of 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$. This area was scanned 10-15 times. Afterwards we have retracted the cantilever and we switched to non-contact mode imaging. We set a larger scan size (10 μm x 10 μm) and a scan angle of 90°. All these images revealed a clear groove of 5 μm length and width of 0.3 – 0.6 μm having a rim of the removed material. Then averaged height profiles perpendicular to the scratched rim were analyzed. As thickness we have taken the depth of the groove (being flat) relative to the topography of the sample adjacent to the rim. In a similar way we have analyzed the height profiles of scratches which were made by a steel needle in the center of the samples.

UV studies of complexation of catechol groups in polymerized films with (9-Anthraceneboronic acid) boronic acid

A spin-coated PEG-ClDop₄ film on a quartz substrate was immersed in a spectrophotometric cuvette filled with buffer solutions at pH 7.4 and 2.5 (PBS and Tris buffers respectively). The UV/vis spectra of the immersed film were recorded at the two pH. The slide was then immersed for 30 min in a 1mM solution of 9-anthraceneboronic acid (An-B(OH)₂) in PBS with 1% DMSO, followed by three washing steps with buffer at pH 7.4 before the UV spectrum was taken. Finally the slide was immersed for 30 min in a buffer at pH 2.5 and washed three times with the same buffer before UV measurements.

Estimation of density and concentration of Cl-catechol groups in the films

The surface density of the An-B(OH)₂ – catechol complex and, therefore, the concentration of Cl-catechols in the film, was estimated from the UV spectrum using the equation

$$\Gamma = A_{\lambda} \epsilon_{\lambda}^{-1} N_A$$

Where Γ (molec_s cm⁻²) is the surface density of the chromophore, A_{λ} is the absorbance of the surface layer at a given wavelength, ϵ_{λ} (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) is the absorbance coefficient of the chromophore in solution at λ and N_A is the Avogadro's number. The absorbance coefficient of

the complex of 9-Anthraceneboronic acid with Cl-dopamine and Dopamine at 362 nm in PBS at pH 7.4 were $\epsilon_{362} = 5068.6$ and $5181.6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The concentration of the Cl-dopamine groups in the film was estimated from the value of the surface density divided by the thickness of the swollen films as obtained by ellipsometry.

Piezorheology experiments

The mechanical properties of the gels were investigated with a homemade piezorheometer.¹⁹⁻²⁰ The sample was placed between two glass slides (area 2 cm^2) with a gap of $100 \mu\text{m}$ between them. A defined shear deformation was applied with a piezoactuator and the stress transmitted through the sample was measured with a second piezoactuator. $8 \mu\text{l}$ of a 200 mg/ml solution of PEG-Dop₄ or PEG-ClDop₄ in H₂O was mixed with $8 \mu\text{l}$ of a 10 mM solution of NaIO₄ in H₂O. After mixing, $15 \mu\text{l}$ of the mixture were placed in the rheometer cell. Measurements started ca. 5 min after mixing. In order to avoid water evaporation during measurements, polydimethylsiloxane oil was used to seal the sample. Continuous frequency sweeps were performed at 23°C and 0.32% strain from 0.63 to 6300 rad/s . The small amplitudes guaranteed that the sample was measured in the linear response regime. The time evolution of the mechanical parameters was followed until cross-linking was completed, i.e. a plateau was reached. The shear modulus of the cross-linked gels are reported in Fig. S3.

Antibacterial experiments

Bacterial Strains

E. coli K12 wildtype (DSM A498, ATCC 23716) grown overnight at 37°C and 200 rpm in LB-medium were diluted with LB medium to an optical density of 0.1 at 600 nm . The bacteria culture was shaken at 37°C at 200 rpm until the midlogarithmic phase was reached ($\text{OD}_{600} \sim 0.5-0.6$). The final cell density was adjusted to $\text{OD}_{600} \sim 0.5$ that corresponds approximately to $1.25 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU/mL}$. (CFU=colony-forming unit)

Inhibition of Bacterial Adhesion

Bacterial adhesion tests were performed on round cover slips (d=13mm) coated with the different Cl-dopamine containing films. 2 mL of *E. coli* bacterial suspension ($\sim 2.5 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL) was added to each well of a sterile 6-well plate. Slides with or without a film coating were immersed in the bacterial suspension for 1 hour at 37 °C. The substrates were washed three times with phosphate buffered saline (without Ca/Mg, Invitrogen, Germany) to remove loosely adhered bacteria. The adherent bacteria on the substrate were stained using SYTO[®] 9 green fluorescent dye for 10 min. Samples were placed on clean microscope slides and visualized using an epifluorescent microscope fitted with a camera. The number of bacteria in each image was obtained by counting five areas of the image. The total number of adherent cells was calculated as percentage of number of adherent bacteria on control (glass cover slide) to number of adherent bacteria on the sample under study. Assays were performed in triplicate.

Bacterial adhesion were analyzed with a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and reported as *p*-values. ANOVA was performed using Microcal Origin software; *p*-values of less than 0.05 suggest differences are statistically significant respect to the control.

Dynamic Contact Assay

E. coli bacterial suspensions were diluted with PBS to 2.5×10^5 CFU/ml. Cover slides coated with the Cl-Dop and Dop- derived films were place in 15ml sterile tubes and incubated with 5 ml of bacterial suspension at 37 °C and 300 rpm for 1 hour. At the end of the incubation time the bacterial suspension was serially diluted and 50 µl was plated on LB-agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Bacteria survival was expressed as number of CFU of bacteria in solution per ml.

Agar Diffusion Test

E. coli bacterial suspensions were diluted using PBS to 1×10^7 CFU/mL and 50 µL from this dilution was spread on the LB agar plates (d = 50 mm). Round cover slides (r = 13 mm), coated with the films, were subsequently placed on LB agar plates with a diameter of 50 mm and bacteria were grown over night at 37 °C.

Antibacterial activity of Cl-dopamine in solution

E.coli bacterial suspensions were prepared as described above and diluted using PBS with different concentration of Cl-dopamine to 2.5×10^5 CFU/ml. The different bacterial suspension were incubated in a 24-well plate for 1 hour, serially diluted and 50 μ l was plated on LB-agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Cell survival was expressed as number of CFU of bacteria in solution per ml.

Cell viability after attachment to Dop and Cl-Dop modified gelatine coatings

Human cervix carcinoma cells (HeLa) were maintained at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in Dulbecco's modified Eagle media (DMEM, Invitrogen) containing 10% fetal calf serum (FCS) and 100 U/mL of penicillin/streptomycin. The cells were harvested using 0.25% trypsin, counted, and resuspended in the cell culture media at a concentration of 5×10^4 cells/mL. 1 ml of this suspension was seeded in the wells of a 24-well plate containing substrates modified with Gel-CIDop, Gel-Dop or Gelatine and incubated (37 °C with 5% CO₂) for 24 hours. The medium was removed and the substrates were washed with PBS in order to eliminate non adherent cells. The amount of cells attached to the substrates was evaluated by optical microscopy and cell viability was quantified with the PrestoBlue assay. Cells were incubated with 900 μ L of fresh medium and 100 μ L of PrestoBlue reagent for 20 min. The fluorescence was measured using a plate reader Infinite M1000 (Tecan, Germany) by using i-control software (Tecan, Germany). The excitation wavelength was 566 nm (\pm 5 nm), and detection wavelength was 590 nm (\pm 5 nm). The average baseline fluorescence measured for control media without cells (negative control) was subtracted from all results to obtain the sample fluorescence. This was normalized by the values measured for control media seeded with cells (positive control). All experiments were performed in triplicate.

Cell viability after incubation with eluted media from Cl-Dop containing gels

Substrates coated with CIDop-modified hydrogels (13 mm in diameter) were placed in 24-well plates and covered with 500 μ L of cell culture medium (without serum). Control experiments with medium added to wells without substrates were prepared in parallel.

HT1080 cells (CCL-121, ATCC, Manassas, VA) were cultured at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in Dulbecco's modified Eagle media (DMEM) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 100 U/mL of penicillin/streptomycin. The cells were harvested using 0.25% trypsin, counted, and resuspended in cell culture media at a concentration of 5×10^5 cells/mL. 100 μ l of this suspension (5000 cells) were seeded in wells of a 96-well plate and incubated (37 °C with 5%

CO₂) for 24, 48 and 76 hours. After this time, the medium was replaced by 100 µl of the test medium and incubated for 6 hours. The viability of HT1080 cells (CCL-121, ATCC, Manassas, VA) was tested with the PrestoBlue cell proliferation assay (Life Technologies, Invitrogen) as described above, but here , the medium was replaced by 90 µL of fresh medium and 10 µL of PrestoBlue reagent and incubated at cell culture conditions for 20 min. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1: Possible reaction products during oxidation and self-polymerization of PEG-CIDop₄

Figure S2: (A) ^1H -NMR spectra of PEG-CIDop₄ in D₂O before and after addition of oxidant at increasing reaction times. 600 μl of a 25 mg/mL solution of PEG-CIDop₄ in D₂O were mixed with 7.5 μl of 200 mM NaIO₄ solution in D₂O in the NMR tube and the spectra were measured at 298.3 K. The molar concentration of CIDop and NaIO₄ in the mixture was 2.5 μM NaIO₄. The proton peaks **a** and **b**, attributed to the aromatic protons of PEG-CIDop₄, disappeared immediately after adding oxidant, indicating instantaneous oxidation of the catechol unit. The new protons **h** and **g** were attributed to the aromatic protons of the ortho-quinone derivative (Figure S1), according to literature data²¹ and they disappeared with increasing reaction time due to oxidant consumption. The protons **c-f** appeared first and disappeared for longer reaction times while a broad signal in 6.5-8.0 ppm range became more visible. Protons **c-f** were attributed to either peroxide intermediates (Figure S1) or biphenyl crosslinking products which became broad with increasing reaction time due to the higher crosslinking degree and increased viscosity of the solution.²² After 10 h reaction time, weak signals of protons **a** and **b** reappeared in the spectrum, presumably because the high viscosity of the system did not allow further crosslinking reactions. Assuming that the intensity of the proton signals of the PEG chain did not change with the crosslinking reaction, the ratio of not crosslinked CIDop terminal groups in the gel could be estimated from the ratio of integrals of residual **a** and **b** signals with that of PEG. This is shown in figure (B). (B) ^1H -NMR spectra of PEG-CIDop₄ in D₂O before and after oxidation with NaIO₄ at 90°C for 2h (see A for details about mixture conditions). A 41% of not crosslinked CIDop terminal groups (ratio between the integrals of the signals of **b** to that of PEG chain) was found (a value of 42% was obtained when estimated from **a**).

The measurements were performed with a 5 mm PAQXI $^1\text{H}/^{19}\text{F}/\text{D}-^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}$ with z-gradient on a 700 MHz spectrometer with a Bruker Advance III system. ^1H spectra were recorded with 128 transients. The 90° pulse was 13,8 μs long, with a spectral width of 12600 Hz and a recycling delay of 5 s. The spectra were measured in D₂O and were referenced by the residual HDO signal at $\delta(^1\text{H}) = 4,71$ ppm. The temperature was held at 298.3 K and regulated by a standard ^1H methanol NMR sample using the topspin 3.1 software (Bruker).

Figure S3: A) UV spectra of 0.1mM dopamine and Cl-dopamine solutions at pH7,5. B) UV spectra of quartz substrates after immersion in a solution of dopamine and Cl-dopamine at different ratios.

Figure S4: Dry thickness of Dop and Cl-Dop coatings as measured by X-Ray Reflectivity, AFM and Ellipsometry.

Table S1: Ellipsometric thickness of dry hydrogel films

Film	Thickness (nm)	S. D. (nm)
Hyal-Dop	15,54	0.53
Hyal-ClDop	12,00	0.70
Alg-ClDop	8,23	0,11
Alg-ClDop	6,44	0,31
Gel-ClDop	8,37	0,26
Gel-ClDop	7,60	0,55

Figure S5: The frequency spectra of crosslinked PEG-Dop₄ and PEG-ClDop₄ gels at T=23°C obtained by piezorheology.

Figure S6: Antibacterial activity of Cl-dopamine in solution: number of CFU/ml *E. coli* in a bacterial solution with different concentrations of Cl-dopamine. * Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) ** Significant differences ($P < 0.01$) *** Significant differences ($P < 0.001$) compared with the control (Glass cover slide)

Figure S7. Agar diffusion test of glass discs treated with Hyal-ClDop and PEG-ClDop₄ and their controls (Hyal-Dop and PEG-Dop₄). No zone of inhibition was shown in the Cl-dopamine modified gels, indicating no leakage of the biocide Cl-dopamine from the gels.

Figure S8: Dynamic Contact Assay: number of CFU/ml of *E. coli* in a bacterial solution after incubation with films containing Dop and Cl-Dop modified polymers. *Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) compared with the control (Glass cover slide)

Figure S9. A) Cell viability as obtained with the PrestoBlue viability assay for the different substrates expressed relative to control. B) Cell viability obtained with the PrestoBlue cell viability assay on HT1080 cells after incubation with the eluent from Dop/Cl-Dop modified substrates for 24, 48 and 76 hours.

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